

**EFFECTIVE METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING
ENGLISH LANGUAGE.**

Isakova Barchinoy Ne'matovna

*English teacher of Fergana Academic lyceum, Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Barchinoyisakova89@gmail.com

Introduction: The language plays a very important role in our life. Out presidents have been paying much attention to learn languages, especially, English since the independence. So nearly all people know the language. They help us express our emotions. They help us explain what we want and to communicate and hence are the prime tools to express who we are. Thus the knowledge of a language and its proper utilization is very important as it defines us. If languages were not there to help us communicate there would be no difference in our communications and the way the animals communicate. Hence the ways the languages are taught play a very vital role in a person's life.

Nowadays all countries over the world pay much attention to the educational system. Because education is considered as the mirror of the country's intelligence. On the other hand, the future of the countries is assessed by the youth. They are the future of every nation. Therefore, we achieve this success by the education. On this way teachers attempt to have the lessons with modern technology and different methods. Method is a Greek word means "the way to something". The method of teaching is the way of organizing the activity of student and teacher for achieving to the aim on the appointed education system. We use a majority of methods in teaching process. Actually, they help to provide the lessons to be more effective and interesting.

Topic analysis: From year to year methods are changed and replaced its place to another. Nowadays we have a great number of methods that we can use in our lesson effectively. Modern methods are divided into 4 large groups. Among them we can use Venn diagram, “Why” and “How” diagrams, Case study method for developing the critical thinking and speaking skills of the student, “think way “ method for the grammar part and other methods.

Among these above methods lecture, explanation, demonstration, working with books, educational games, exercises, brain- storming, and conversational-debate methods are widely used. The aim of these methods is to serve enlarging the students world –out looking and improving their speaking. This research work analyses the innovative and quite interesting methods we have in teaching English language. We may have a number of teaching methods in between traditional and modern. Everybody has their own understanding and conclusions on teaching English language. But this research work portrays combining this two types how we can make our teaching very effective. We have been completely bounded with traditional methods of teaching and understanding where the present day learners felt uncomfortable a bit. Learner’s mind will never be static it is ever growing and ever changing. Whatever the teaching methodology can be, but teaching must be learners centered. However, this work scrutinizes the difference between traditional and practical teaching and thereafter learning. This treatise practically examines that how learners are being affected by the traditional methods of teaching as well, besides it has portrayed that how learners expect teaching and learning process. There has been a misunderstanding between traditional methods and practical methods always. Somehow teachers and learners should agree each other in order to fill the gap between the generations of these methods. ¹

English, the official language of the entire world is a very tricky language to teach. In fact every language varies to teach. English is a very old

language and has undergone many forms changes from Proto English derived from the Latin and the German culture to the Modern English which was established after in the post Renaissance period. Each version was simpler than it's previous. Present day English is the simplest adaptation of a very old Language and yet it is difficult to teach this language effectively especially to those who speak English as a second language. In today's world English is taught in a very orthodox manner. The basic teaching is needed. Teaching the alphabets and the formations of the word is essential and a must. But there is something that is even more important. The children must be able to speak the words and understand their meaning before writing them down. The foundation to teach English can only be taught using the orthodox methods of teaching the alphabets and the words. But then teaching only the rules is found to be boring by most students and it is because of this that they lose interest in learning the language. Although there is no way other than the traditional one to teach the basics of the language these methods must be tweaked a bit so as to appeal to the students. When it comes to teaching English to students of higher classes who already know the basics the traditional methods implemented like use of stories, poems, movies, books and newspapers. These methods help the students learn the language better without them actually realizing and also it keeps their interest. This work will provide a few of such methods to teach English language.

Enacting the stories. Stories form a very integral part of teaching a language. These stories help teach the students about the formation of sentences and how to express their thoughts and a lot of other things and plus they help in keeping the students interest alive as the story's end is something that every student wants to know. It appeals to the inquisitive nature of the students. Any unfinished story always keeps the mind of the reader agitated.

Although this method of using stories has been implemented the procedure of teaching the language through it is generally not right. The

evaluation procedure of testing the students in their proficiency over the language is through questions based on the story. This is generally not that effective. Due to this the students generally tend to take up the stories as a chapter rather than looking at it as an interesting read. A story is supposed to appeal to the creative part of the brain. It helps us be more imaginative, by trying to visualize the things that are happening inside the story. It should not only teach them the language but it should also help them in extracting a lesson from the story. Keeping questions for evaluation kills the entire idea of imagination for the students look at the story as something that they need to learn for answers.

There is a better way of using the stories to English using stories. The students can enact the stories or the plays. In this way the students are personally engaged with the stories. They can bring their own interpretation of the character to life. It is interesting for the students to understand the characters and put themselves in their positions. It engages their creativity by allowing them to create the entire set, assign the characters and play it out according to what they had imagined. It also helps them understand other people's interpretation of the story and helps them have a healthy conversation about it which again helps them in learning the language. It removes the dull aspects and makes the learning more colorful without jeopardizing the learning of the language. It may not be perfect but it will leave a deep impression on their mind.

The story will help them learn the language as they will be enacting it by dialog which they will themselves extract from the stories and also modifications can be made to the plays to help the students be more interactive and creative. They can add more lines, characters change the ending, bring in an interesting twist etc. The more creative the modification, more are the points awarded to the team. This also leads to personality development and helps them work as a team player and all the way the student was learning the

language.

For example if Julius Caesar was taught using the traditional methods of questions and answers the student would never understand the deep emotions of Brutus, the cunningness of Cassius, the loyalty of Antony, the tragedy of war, the brilliance in Antony's speech and many other such aspects of the story for which the Carol, Harry Porter, and all the epic stories. Emotions help define the story and they form a very important aspect of the language and one's personality. If these emotions are left out then it would be very difficult to express ourselves. On the other hand if such stories are enacted then every intention of the story becomes clear. The students have to immerse themselves into the atmosphere of the story and they have to put them in their positions. This entire process has many benefits besides being a very effective method of teaching the language; it helps preserve the literature, which is nothing but our culture. This method brings about the total learning experience that was meant to be provided by the story and in the end the student will definitely be able to answer questions without even preparing for it as an exam, besides the entire process is fun and not at all boring. Hence it ensures the learning process is complete.

Teaching through conversations. Conversations are by far the most useful ways of teaching the language. When a child learns his or her mother tongue it is by the conversations made by the others. The child is never taught the language but is still able to percept the meaning and learns it automatically to use it in day to day life. No one ever teaches the kids the characters of the language or how to make sentences or the grammar of that language. The conversations alone teach the children.

Hence conversations form a very important part of the teaching process. The sentence construction and the grammar is not something that can be entirely taught by rules. They have to be taught intuitively. That can only happen through a lot of reading and a lot of listening. This can be taken care of easily as every conversation needs a topic. The topic can be given to the

students in form of written documents which they have to first read then form an opinion and then have a conversation about it or it can be spoken out and then they can listen, understand and also take part in the conversation.

The participation and other aspects of the conversation can always be evaluated through points which will also push the students to take part in the conversation. These conversations have to be general. They have to happen as if and children generally tend to like games and want to play them more and more. Traditional methods dictated for study and games to be separate but the fact remains that the students tend to be more interested in playing games rather than sitting down to study. Any logical reasoning would dictate us to combine the two aspects to solve the problem. The games part of learning would help the students keep their interest as the desire to win is very strong. It keeps us going and when included with different aspects of learning the learning process would continue almost throughout the day without the children getting tired or bored of studying.

Conclusion: In formation of interest to a subject the huge role is played by the person of the teacher. Therefore a pledge of successful mastering a foreign language by the students is professionalism of the teacher which should in the work not only take into account the methodical principles underlying teaching, but also to be in constant search of new receptions and means of teaching which will recover a lesson, will make it fascinating, cognitive and remembered.

The most useful for his purpose are the following receptions and methods: methods of constructivism, communicative methods, methods of projects and discussions, games and role games, etc.

In use work have been analysed all these methods and the receptions raising quality of training to foreign language on the basis of studying of various techniques of teaching, used in work with children and students. Many of receptions can be applied with success at teaching children of younger and

more advanced age. The resulted techniques are interesting from many points of view, simple in application and can add essentially existing operating time of teachers foreign (including English) language. While some of the methods are let be omitted by the teacher (like silent way, synthetic or analytic (every teacher choose his own way to work with students) all of these must be included in the learning process. giving you a full length of techniques to apply within one method. They don't give strict directions of how to apply them but a wide space for creative work.

References:

1. Негневицкая Е.И., Никитенко З.Н., Артамонова И.А. Книга для учителя. М., Просвещение, 1997.
2. Витт Н.В. Эмоциональное воздействие речи учителя иностранного языка. // Иностранные языки в школе. - 1999. - №6. – с. 34
3. Brown, H. D. (2001). Teaching by principles: An attractive approach to language pedagogy. New York: Longman
4. Berer, Marge and Frank, Christine and Rinvoluceri, Mario. Challenge to think. Oxford University Press, 2002
5. A. TAKALA. 2016. Department of languages. “Grammar teaching methods in EFL lessons”
6. V. Boumova. “Modern Teaching Methods” 2015
7. Terry Heick. “12 strategies for Teaching Literatures in the 21 centure”2018
8. N.Mediha. “ A Comparative study on the effectiveness of using methods”2014

<http://www.sse-franchise.com/soapbox/200703/16/what-is-the-communicative-teaching-method/>

<http://www.yanglish.ru/catalog2/englishlanguage.htm>

<http://e.usia.gov/forum/vols/vol36/no1/p20.htm-games>

<http://www.reseach gate. Net file>

<http://www.iosjournals org papers version-4.>